

Thornhill's Contributions

Sirish L. Shah*

*Emeritus Professor at the University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada (e-mail: sirish.shah@ualberta.ca)

Abstract: This article describes Nina's contributions over her career as observed by a close colleague at the University of Alberta, Canada. Nina Thornhill is very modest about her contributions; what is clear and well known is that she has made transformative and foundational contributions to the broad field of analytics. The impact of her work has been far and wide. Nina spent a sabbatical at the University of Alberta, Canada, in 2000/2001. During this time and subsequently she collaborated with Sirish Shah and many of his graduate students and researchers. This tribute on her retirement, narrated through images and notes, is a simple summary of her many contributions.

Keywords: Controller performance monitoring, sabbatical, University of Alberta, multivariate time trends, valve stiction, gifted mentor.

1. INTRODUCTION

It was 1998/9 or thereabout when Nina first visited the University of Alberta during one of her Canadian visits. It was also the time when Controller Performance Monitoring was attracting a lot of attention from academia and industry. Nina gave an insightful seminar on her application work in this area with industry and so naturally we explored ways of collaboration.

We were overjoyed and fortunate to have her spend an entire year 2000/2001 on a sabbatical at the University of Alberta. She did not mind the cold and I even recall that she would climb a steep hill to work from her river view apartment. The time she spent at the U of Alberta turned out to be a very productive year not just from a research publications view point but from the transformative work that came from Nina's precision analytics skill set.

Fig. 1. January 2001, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada: From right to left: Nina Thornhill, Sirish Shah, the late Grant Fisher and Siegfried Wanke (Chair of Chemical Engineering).

Nina's remarkable aptitude is to not just to see and analyze a 'few trees in a forest' but to look for the BIG picture and explore analytics from a holistic perspective. What flowed out of her creative palette were simple but powerful ideas that have broad appeal not just in the context of the process industry but broadly applicable to other areas as well. Her message was:

- Do not just look at univariate trends in data records. Look at all the data collectively and cohesively in a multivariate framework. Towards this end she developed the 'High density time trends', See Fig 3.
- Look at data in the temporal as well as spectral domains. See Fig. 4.
- Explore different ways of data visualization; so rather than looking at correlation numbers look at a pixelated picture of the correlation numbers in the temporal as well as the spectral domains. See Fig. 5.

Fig. 2. Nina at the U of A faculty club during her sabbatical at the University of Alberta (January 2001).

Fig. 3. High density time series plots of process data.

Nina is gifted mentor. She built strong rapport with many graduate students during her time at the U of A as evident from the many joint publications that followed with graduate students and researchers. It was also Nina's precision skill set and that knack for detailed insight and analysis that led to the development of a model for a sticky valve with Shoukat Choudhury. I had asked Shoukat to investigate the role of higher order statistics to detect and diagnose valve problems, a project that required signal processing ideas. Shoukat was a graduate student supervised jointly by Nina and myself and spent a few months at UCL under Nina's guidance. What came out were many highly cited publications and a book. See Fig. 6 to 12. See notes from Shoukat Choudhury.

In this article, Nina's contributions as an internationally renowned Professor are detailed. She has had a remarkable and productive research career where she has developed:

- Informative visual analytic ideas: Simple yet powerful tools that have laid the foundation for temporal and spectral analysis of process data;
- Valve stiction: detection, modeling and quantification;
- Impact of compression on process data analytics;
- Her work has sparked wide-spread interest in data based causality or process topology capture, and
- Many more recent ideas including kernel based methods applicable to non-linear systems....

2. POWERFUL VISUAL ANALYTICS TOOLS

Fig. 4. High density temporal and spectral plots of process data.

Fig. 5. Clustered power spectral correlation plot of process data to clearly show tags that have similar spectral shapes.

2. VALVE STICTION WORK (WITH S. CHOUDHURY)

This was a pioneering study that required careful problem formulation, modeling and analysis. Ideally suited for a person with perfection skills that Nina has.

Fig. 6. Experimental setup for valve stiction.

Fig. 7. Schematic of a valve with to indicate causes of stiction due to valve packing.

Fig. 8. Springer book on Diagnosis of Process Nonlinearities and Valve Stiction.

Fig. 9. Stiction: A closer look.

Fig. 10 shows a level control loop, which controls the level of condensate in the outlet of a turbine in a power plant by manipulating the flow rate of the liquid condensate.

Fig. 8. Industrial Case Study: Level Control of Turbine Condensate to detect valve stiction.

Quantification of stiction

Fig. 10. Validation of the stiction detection and quantification algorithm .

3. PIONEERING IDEAS ON DATA BASED PROCESS CONNECTIVITY

Basic idea: Faults propagate throughout the plant and so it is not easy to find the root cause of such faults. So how do we capture the material and information flow path in the process using data? This was ground breaking work by Nina and Bauer and the entire study has spawned much research in including process connectivity or topology in the field of analytics. Nina has inspired many researchers to continue working in this area including one of my own student, Ping Duan. See the note from Ping Duan.

3.1 Eastman Chemical Benchmark Study

Fig. 11. P&ID plot of the Eastman process.

3.2 Time Trends and Power Spectra of Measurements

Fig. 12. Identification of root cause of common oscillations.

It was assumed that the common oscillation in Fig. 11 is probably generated within a certain control loop. 14 controlled process variables corresponding to 14 PID controller loops are available. The power spectra indicate the presence of oscillation at the frequency of about 0.003 cycles/sample, nearly a period of 2 hours, our goal is to detect and diagnose the root cause of this oscillation. The following eight process variables have common oscillations LC1.pv (denoted by x_1), FC1.pv (denoted by x_2), TC1.pv (denoted by x_3), PC2.pv (denoted by x_4), FC5.pv (denoted by x_5), LC2.pv (denoted by x_6), FC8.pv (denoted by x_7), and TC2.pv (denoted by x_8).

It is assumed that if a variable does not show significant power at the common oscillation frequency, then the root cause of the common oscillation is unlikely to be within its control loop. Therefore, we only need to find the information flow pathways among these variables that have oscillations at the oscillation frequency

4. ABOUT NINA'S RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Articulate research with lasting contributions

In many ways Nina's ideas have been transformative in the broad field of process data analytics where she was one of the first players. Her approach to analytics has been quite remarkable: very much a hands-on approach in analytics. She is a proficient and very organized book-keeper, a skill that is so important when you analyse tons of data.

The Thornhill way: Precise, meticulous and tidy book-keeping. Always well organized. Even her pencil case/purse is so well organized!!

4.2 A gifted mentor

A gifted and valued researcher and mentor. I recall Shoukat Choudhury (who was co-supervised by Nina and I) recalling Nina's comments on the use of the term 'etc..' while proof reading a joint paper that we were writing. Nina would say,

“ ‘etc or etcetra’ is simply a synonym for being lazy. It is better to be very specific and so let's not use this term...”

4.3 Poised and careful manner of speech and articulate discussant.

Please see note from Ping Duan. She was surely inspired by Nina's thoughtful comments and directions in her work.

4.4 Nina's influence has spread wide and far

Fig. 12 and the detail in Fig. 13 is a poster that Professor Iwai has archived for a meeting held in Kumamoto, Japan in 2002. He sends warm regards to Nina. Poster shows the words 'June 9' erupting out of Mount Aso (an active volcano)!! The detail advertises the pre-symposium workshop: "How well is your controller performing: Good, Bad or Optimal?" by S.L. Shah, B. Huang and N.F. Thornhill.

She has a big following in Canada, India and China and of course in Europe, USA and Africa!

Fig. 12. Prof. Iwai with poster of AdCONIP02, held in Kumamoto, Japan in 2002. See zoomed portion below for Nina Thornhill's participation in a workshop on controller performance monitoring.

Fig. 13. Detail from poster of Fig. 12.

In ending this note, I wish Nina a happy, joyful and healthy retirement. For her dedication and hard work she deserves the best retirement ever. Perhaps this will be the beginning of the second innings onto something very exciting. Good luck and may your retirement be filled with new adventures, meaningful moments and much happiness.

REFERENCES

- Choudhury, M. S., Thornhill, N. F., & Shah, S. L. (2005). Modelling valve stiction. *Control engineering practice*, 13(5), 641-658.
- Choudhury, M. S., Shah, S. L., & Thornhill, N. F. (2004). Diagnosis of poor control-loop performance using higher-order statistics. *Automatica*, 40(10), 1719-1728.
- Choudhury, M. S., Shah, S. L., Thornhill, N. F., & Shook, D. S. (2006). Automatic detection and quantification of stiction in control valves. *Control engineering practice*, 14(12), 1395-1412.
- Thornhill, N. F., Shah, S. L., Huang, B., & Vishnubhotla, A. (2002). Spectral principal component analysis of dynamic process data. *Control Engineering Practice*, 10(8), 833-846.
- Thornhill, N. F., Patwardhan, S. C., & Shah, S. L. (2008). A continuous stirred tank heater simulation model with applications. *Journal of Process Control*, 18(3-4), 347-360.
- Choudhury, A. A. S., Shah, S. L., & Thornhill, N. F. (2008). Diagnosis of process nonlinearities and valve stiction: data driven approaches. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Thornhill, N. F., Choudhury, M. S., & Shah, S. L. (2004). The impact of compression on data-driven process analyses. *Journal of Process Control*, 14(4), 389-398.
- Tangirala, A. K., Shah, S. L., & Thornhill, N. F. (2005). PSCMAP: A new tool for plant-wide oscillation detection. *Journal of Process Control*, 15(8), 931-941.
- Choudhury, M. S., Thornhill, N. F., & Shah, S. L. (2004). A data-driven model for valve stiction. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 37(1), 245-250.
- Thornhill, N. F., Huang, B., & Shah, S. L. (2003). Controller performance assessment in set point tracking and regulatory control. *International Journal of Adaptive Control and Signal Processing*, 17(7-9), 709-727.
- Choudhury, M. A. A. S., Shah, S. L., & Thornhill, N. F. (2002). Detection and diagnosis of system nonlinearities using higher order statistics. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 35(1), 337-342.
- Choudhury, M. S., Kariwala, V., Shah, S. L., Douke, H., Takada, H., & Thornhill, N. F. (2005). A simple test to confirm control valve stiction. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 38(1), 81-86.
- Shoukat Choudhury, M. A. A., Kariwala, V., Thornhill, N. F., Douke, H., Shah, S. L., Takada, H., & Forbes, J. F. (2007). Detection and diagnosis of plant-wide oscillations. *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 85(2), 208-219.
- Choudhury, M. A. A. S., Shah, S. L., & Thornhill, N. F. (2012). U.S. Patent No. 8,145,328. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Thornhill, N. F., Shah, S. L., & Huang, B. (2000). Detection and diagnosis of unit-wide oscillations. *Process Control and Instrumentation*, 26.
- Huang, B., Thornhill, N. F., Shah, S. L., & Shook, D. (2002). Path analysis for process troubleshooting.
- Thornhill, N. F., & Shah, S. L. (2005). New directions in control loop assessment and diagnosis. *Computing and Control Engineering*, 16(4), 18-22.
- Thornhill, N. F., Shah, S. L., & Huang, B. (2000). Controller performance assessment in set point tracking and regulatory control. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 33(10), 183-188.